

Entropy, Information and Average Energy for the Bose-Einstein, Fermi-Dirac and Kaniadakis Statistics

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In an earlier note (1), we argued that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) case, temperature times entropy equals the average energy minus temperature times the log of the distribution normalization constant divided by V . This is interesting because Helmholtz free energy $E-TS$ then equals a term dependent essentially on the log of the distribution normalization constant. The normalization constant (in one dimension) for a Gaussian is related to standard deviation which is related to T , temperature, so free energy (in one dimension) is related to the log of this spread (standard deviation) of the distribution. In higher dimensions, $\ln(T)$ still emerges. In this note, we wish to extend the ideas of (1) to the case of the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac statistics for nonrelativistic kinematics. Entropy is again closely related to average energy. In addition, the distribution normalization constant becomes connected to the fugacity, at least in the MB limit. Entropy density is no longer $-f(e/T) \ln(g(e/T))$ where $f(e/T)$ =distribution = $B g(e/T)$ where B is the normalization constant. There is an additional term which is proportional to: $g(e/T)[\ln(g(e/T)) - \ln(g_{MB}(e/T))]$ i.e. the average of the difference of the information for the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein case and the Boltzmann. We also consider the relationship between the distribution constant B and fugacity and then apply these ideas to the Kaniadakis distribution.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, entropy follows from the Boltzmann-Gibbs-Shannon form:

$$S/k = - \sum_e f(e/T) \ln[f(e/T)]$$

This in turn may be written in terms of average energy and a term related to the natural log of the normalization constant. The natural log of the normalization constant is proportional to $\ln(T)$ where T , the temperature, is related to the standard deviation of the Gaussian distribution. Thus, the free energy $E-TS = NT \ln(B/V)$ where $f(e/T)=B \exp(-e/T)$ is proportional to $\ln(T)$ which is the log of the spread of the Gaussian. When dealing with $f(e/T)$ it is natural to normalize f i.e. introduce B . Interestingly, for the grand canonical case used for Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein statistics, one deals with fugacity, $\exp(u/T)$ where u is the chemical potential and $n(e/T)$ where n is the average number of particles in e/T . Thus, the normalization constant does not appear explicitly, but is related to the fugacity as is shown later. It is also interesting to note that the entropy for the MB case depends so closely on average energy with only an extra term related to $T \ln(T)$ which in turn is related to $\ln(B)$ representing a spread in the system included.

Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein Cases

From (2), one has for entropy:

$$S/k = \sum_i d(i) \left[\frac{b e_i - \ln(z)}{z^{-1} \exp(b e_i) - 1} - \ln(1 - z \exp(-b e_i)) \right] \quad \text{Bose-Einstein ((1a))}$$

$$S/k = \sum_i d(i) \left[\frac{b e_i - \ln(z)}{z^{-1} \exp(b e_i) - 1} + \ln(1 + z \exp(-b e_i)) \right] \quad \text{Fermi-Dirac ((1b))}$$

$$S/k = z \sum_i d(i) \exp(-b e_i) (b e_i - \ln(z)) \quad \text{MB ((1c))}$$

Here, $b=1/kT$ and $d(i) = d^3r d^3p / (h^3)$ We set $k=h=1$ going forward.

z is the fugacity $\exp(u/T)$ where u is the chemical potential.

One may immediately notice that entropy is again directly related to the average energy which is perhaps the motivation for defining a Helmholtz free energy $E-TS$ (apart from the thermodynamic differential reason which changes TdS into $-SdT$). A second point to note is that:

$$n(e_i) = d(i) / [z^{-1} \exp(b e_i) \mp 1] \quad \text{Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac ((2a))}$$

$$\text{And } \sum_i n(e_i) = N \text{ the number of particles. ((2b))}$$

From ((2a)) and ((2b)) one sees that "normalization" is not explicitly present. For example, one may take the high e_i limit of ((2a)) to obtain $n(e_i) \text{ (MB)} = z \exp(-b e_i)$. If N is set to 1, then z , it seems, should play the role of a normalization constant. (This is of importance for the MB definition of entropy - $\sum_i d(i) \ln(f(e_i)/T)$ where the normalization constant carries much of the physics, especially for the Helmholtz free energy.)

The connection between z , the fugacity, and the MB distribution normalization follows from (2) i.e.

$$N = z \sum_i d(i) \exp(-b e_i) \quad \text{where } d(i) = V \int d^3p \quad \text{and } e_i = p^2/2m$$

$$\text{Then } N = zV (mT/6.28)^{-3} \quad B1 = B/V = (1/V) (mT/6.28)^3 \quad \text{and } z = N/V (mT/6.28)^3$$

Thus, if $N=1$, then $B=z$, so the fugacity plays the role of the normalization constant in the MB case. This is interesting because one does not need to explicitly carry a normalization constant. For example, in the case of the Kaniadakis distribution:

$f(e/T) = [\sqrt{1 + k^2 x^2} + kx]^{1/k}$ Setting $k=0$ yields the MB distribution with $x = b(e-u)$ where u is the chemical potential. Thus, one obtains $z \exp(-b e)$ which is normalized as seen from above with $N=1$.

Shannon Information Form

The entropy density for the Fermi Dirac and Bose Einstein distributions is not of the Boltzmann-Gibbs-Shannon form - $f(e/T) \ln[f(e/T)]$. In (3), it is shown that only a generalized MB

distribution is compatible with Shannon's entropy. One may, however, express ((1a)) or ((1b)) in a form which involves Shannon's entropy and another term which seems to be related to information. We consider ((1a)) here.

Let $g(e_i) = z \exp(-b e_i) / [1 - z \exp(-b e_i)]$. Then:

$b e_i = -\ln(g) + \ln(z) - \ln(1 - z \exp(-b e_i))$ or S/k density = $-g \ln(g) - 2 g \ln[1 - z \exp(-b e_i)]$ from ((1a)) and:

$-2 g \ln[1 - z \exp(-b e_i)] = 2 g \ln[g z^{-1} \exp(b e_i)] = 2 g \{ \ln(g) - \ln(g_{MB}) \}$ where $g_{MB} = z \exp(-b e_i)$

Thus, S/k density Bose-Einstein = Shannon's entropy form - 2 the average (with the BE distribution) of the difference in BE and MB informations. A similar result holds for the Fermi Dirac case. Thus, it seems the Bose Einstein and Fermi Dirac entropies are linked to the idea of information.

Kaniadakis Entropy

Kaniadakis introduced a distribution (4):

$$f(e) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k^2 x^2} + kx \}^{1/k} \quad ((3))$$

In the limit, $k \rightarrow 0$, the MB distribution is obtained. If one uses $e = b(x - u)$ where $b = 1/T$ and u is the chemical potential (and $N=1$), then for the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit, the MB distribution is already normalized. Thus, it seems one may consider ((3)) as normalized. Kaniadakis presents an entropy in (4), but later papers (5) define a k entropy density as:

$$-f(x) Q(f(x)) \quad \text{where } Q(f(x)) = x \quad \text{where } x = 1/T (-e + u)$$

In such a case, entropy is again closely related to the average energy and free energy to u , the chemical potential:

$$TS \text{ density} = \int d(e_i) e_i f(b(-e_i + u)) + u \int d(e_i) f(b(-e_i + u)) \quad ((4))$$

$d(e_i)$ is the measure of e_i e.g. $V d^3p$. $\int d(e_i) f(b(-e_i + u)) = N$ and if one has $N=1$ or

$TS \text{ density} = E_{ave} + u(T, V)$ where u is the chemical potential.

This seems to be very close to the MB situation where $z=B$, the normalization constant and

$$TS \text{ density} = E_{ave} - T \ln(B/V) = E_{ave} + T \ln(V) + u(T, V)$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to extend some ideas presented in (1) for the MB entropy to the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac nonrelativistic cases. We find that like for the MB case, T times entropy is equal to average energy plus an extra term. For the MB case, this extra term is of the form $T \ln [B/V]$ where B is the normalization constant of the MB distribution. For the grand canonical case, used to derive the Bose Einstein and Fermi Dirac cases, the fugacity z enters and actually becomes B , the normalization constant in the MB case of $N=1$. For the Bose Einstein case, the entropy density may be written as a Shannon's entropy term plus an average (using the BE distribution) of the difference in BE and MB information. A similar result holds for the Fermi Dirac case. It is interesting that if $N=1$, normalization is already contained in the Bose Einstein and Fermi Dirac expressions for the average number of particles in a state $n(e_i)$ ((2a)) ((2b)). The Zaniadakis distribution becomes $z \exp(-\beta e)$ in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit which is normalized, so one may assume, it seems, that the Zaniadakis distribution is normalized. This seems to have consequences on the free energy in the Zaniadakis situation as described above.

References

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